

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING MULTIMEDIA EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY IN THE PROCESS OF ACTIVITIES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Annotation: The article talks about the effectiveness of information technologies and multimedia products in the process of preschool education. The effectiveness of the multimedia platform created as an implementation of the adopted decisions and decrees on the development of the field of preschool education. Information about its use in practice and its effectiveness is provided.

Key words: preschool education, multimedia, information technologies, platform, electronic textbook, preschool education organization.

Today, the use of multimedia technologies in the field of education is becoming widespread. The intended content and purpose of the education intended for the student is to make one student rely on an independent life, to acquire independent knowledge according to the student's own wishes, desires and interests, and to use the acquired knowledge. You have formed the first professional skills to be able to use them effectively. It is important that the use of multimedia technologies is a cost-effective and effective way to fulfill such a task. For this, the teacher should be able to understand the essence of multimedia technologies and be able to keep them in his mind. The concept of multimedia means a complex of tools that process information in a form. Multimedia technologies are a set of tools for processing information in this form. First of all, tavusYag, a video element processing engine, is used in the multimedia technology. In addition, multiplication (animation) and high-quality graphics also belong to the category of multimedia technology. Perhaps, in the future, it will be possible to work with other types of multimedia information, for example, virtual reality.

It is known that multimedia technologies enrich the educational process, educational material allows to make the perception of educational information more effective. Multimedia is an interactive visual and audio effect under the control of interactive software using modern technical and software tools, which combines text, sound, graphics, photo, video in a single digital presentation method. Hypermedia are computer files associated with hypertext media used in multimedia objects. In organizing education using computers and other Internet technologies, along with various advantages, there are also some disadvantages: it can be a problem with communication lines. These problems can be solved using optical compact discs called CD-ROM and DVD discs.

Modern educational tools - interactive, audio-visual, multimedia educational equipment - are not just tools that are becoming fashionable, but also a variable opportunity for the development of students' personality. The task of the modern education system is not only to impart knowledge, but also to help students to develop their creative thinking. Any theoretical knowledge must be strengthened by practice. It is very important to actively involve and interest students in the educational process. The educational process is very effective on the basis of making teaching interesting and involving all students in it with their full thinking. Visual tools play an important role in this, they develop the ability to work with different sources of information and compare the obtained results. As a result of the correct organization of the educational process, first of all, the universal effect of education, and based on it - useful qualifications and skills, and finally a wide range of potentials are formed. Teaching through multimedia programs helps to systematize the content components of educational material on a large scale, allows learners to freely choose and switch to complete or reduced options of education. A new form of educational tools. creates opportunities not only for the creation of new opportunities for communication and information transfer, but also for the creation of new problems, solutions, and new intersection points that are unique in modern culture compared to traditional education and information media. According to the

possibilities of taking into account the individual characteristics of learners and helping to increase their interest (motivation), as well as according to the qualities of compatibility, interactivity, flexibility of various types of multimedia educational information, multimedia is useful and productive education. In technology. Provision of interactivity is one of the important achievements of digital multimedia compared to other means of presenting information. Interactivity refers to providing information relevant to the learner's needs.

Interactivity allows you to control the presentation of information to a certain extent: learners can individually change the settings defined in the program, study the results, respond to the program's request about a specific desire of the user, set the speed of presentation of materials and the number of repetitions. . But it is important to consider a number of aspects when using multimedia. Educational materials presented in multimedia should be easy to understand, presented through modern information and convenient tools. In order to fully reveal all the possibilities of multimedia technologies and use them effectively, a potential (competent) teacher should be provided to learners. support is necessary. As when using textbooks, in the use of multimedia tools, the educational strategy in the educational process is that the teacher not only provides information, but also helps the learners, supports and guides the process. can be enriched with content only when engaged in management. Usually, presentations enriched with beautiful images or animations are more attractive than plain text and can provide the necessary emotional level while complementing the material being presented. To sum up, today multimedia technologies are one of the promising directions of informatization of the educational process.

The introduction of multimedia technologies into the educational process is an important condition for the intellectual development of students and the socio-economic development of our society. For this reason, today's teacher should work tirelessly on himself, possess the qualities necessary for his professional expertise as

a person with broad creative thinking and effective use of advanced pedagogical and multimedia technologies.

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